

Thomas Willis on scurvy (1667)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

This is James Lind's English summary of a text on scurvy by Thomas Willis in 1667, the original was published in Latin. Lind was highly critical on Willis' texts.

Thomas Willis, an English physician, Professor of natural philosophy at Oxford
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=573>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Thomas_Willis

<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/inspiring-physicians/thomas-willis>

<https://history.rcp.ac.uk/blog/thomas-willis-father-neurology>

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsnr.1960.0008>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8105036>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections.

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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Background

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment.
Nutr Rev. 2009 Jun;67(6):315-32.

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2009.00205.x>

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Yet orthodox physicians, such as **Thomas Willis**, Gideon Harvey, Boerhaave, Meade, and Cullen, wrote copiously and learnedly about scurvy, but without any maritime experience, simply listing the many standard theories of the cause of scurvy, and the many standard medical treatments such as bleeding, purging, and polypharmacy. Many of them mentioned treatment with oranges and lemons but without making it clear that sailors and ships' surgeons had long been satisfied that citrus fruits were specific prophylactics and cures for scurvy.

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Lind was well aware of the putative misdiagnosis of scurvy. "Some will perhaps say that these fruits have often been used in the scurvy without success; as appears from the experience of physicians, who prescribe them every day in that disease at land. And here we may again observe the fatal consequences of confounding this malady with others. Legions of distempers (according to **Willis** and others) very different from the real and genuine scurvy, have been classed under its name: and because the most approved antiscorbutics fail to remove such diseases, hence we are told by authors (Boerhaave and many others) that it is the masterpiece of art to cure it ... So that nothing can be more absurd, than to object against the efficacy of these fruits in preventing and curing the real scurvy, because they do not cure very different diseases".¹

Carpenter KJ. The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C. 1986, p.249.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/academic/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

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The system [of scurvy], simplified here, was fully developed and became orthodox under the influence of Hermann Boerhaave (1668 - 1738) at Leyden. Acid was also equated to "hot," and alkali to "cold." With the development of these ideas, scurvy was, of course, one of the diseases that physicians were anxious to classify. We can see at once, however, that there was a difficulty: Pimples and ulcers were a sign of "acid acrimony," whereas stinking breath was the result of putrefaction ("alkaline acrimony"); moreover, there had been a continuing belief that the sailors' scurvy was related to their salt meat's being half-putrefied already.

Thomas Willis, the Oxford professor, skirted the problem in 1667 by saying that the disease could arise from both types of blood conditions - i.e., acid (which he called "sulphureo-saline") or alkaline (which he called "salino-sulphureous"). For the first condition he prescribed repeated bleeding and cooling medicines, and for the second, warming medicines.

1 <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bg2gxrzz/items?canvas=226> p.203-204, 1st ed
<https://archive.org/details/b30507054/page/204/mode/2up> p.203-204, 1st ed
<https://archive.org/details/treatisescurvyt00lind/page/204/mode/2up>

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Turning to the seventeenth-century writers, Lind was particularly critical of Eugeleus, who was largely responsible for describing as “scorbutic,” conditions which were quite different from the characteristic pattern of the disease as it appeared at sea...

Lind apologized for his long treatment of Eugeleus: “his vanity and presumption are indeed intolerable,” but “succeeding authors follow him most religiously and minutely”; at times, “they even exceed him in absurdities.”

For the well-known Oxford professor, **Thomas Willis** (1621— 75), it seemed that any case, “which cannot properly be referred to any disease, may justly be called scorbutic.” For Lind, as for Thomas Sydenham, referred to in the previous chapter, falling back on the term “scorbutic” was a convenience for ignorant and indolent practitioners, “as if an unmeaning term was as requisite in physic as pious frauds in certain religions.”

His skeptical treatment of these ideas, and his insistence on evidence to support theories, provided a refreshing blast of common sense. He was equally critical of the eighteenth-century divisions of scurvy, among others, into “hot or cold,” “acidic or lixivial [alkaline],” “sea or land,” and “hereditary or adventitious.”

Lind's comments on Thomas Willis

p.15-17

Eugalenus had not talents sufficient to form any sort of theory for illustrating the nature of the many diseases referred by him to the scorbutic taint. The principles he assumes upon particular occasions of obstructions in the liver and spleen, overflowing of the *black bile*, and corruption of the humours, are all borrowed from other authors, lamely explained by him, and often contradicted in his book. *Sennertus*'s hypothesis confutes itself. So it was left to Dr. **Willis**, with the assistance of Dr. *Lower*, to clear up a subject that lay under very great obscurity, by reducing the whole into an ingenious system, which continues established and adopted even at this day.

It may be worth while to take notice, that until *Eugalenus*'s time, as before mentioned, putrid gums and swelled legs were the characteristic signs of the scurvy. This last author made them to be a small, quick, and unequal pulse, together with a peculiar state of urine. But such a condition of pulse is not mentioned by **Willis** to have been observed in any of the cases he gives to illustrate his account of this disease; nor is it so much as mentioned in his book, except under the title of the *irregular pulse*, which is said to occur only in the most inveterate scurvy. And although he lays great stress on the appearances in the urine; yet here he in some respects likewise differs from *Eugalenus*.

There is another very material difference in their accounts of this disease. *Eugalenus* found it in his time very easy to remove. Accordingly, his book abounds with some very speedy and miraculous cures. Whereas now the scurvy is become much more obstinate, proceeds from various and opposite causes, requiring very different methods of cure; the simple antiscorbutic herbs being by no means sufficient to remove it.

Willis having given a very different account of this disease from all others; as will appear by comparing the symptoms described by each in the third part of this treatise; in my first edition I examined what singular and distinguishing marks and characteristics he gave of such a variety of distempers, in order to their being with any manner of propriety classed under one denomination, and referred to the disease we are now treating of. I there proved, that the signs given

by him of the scurvy, are at best but doubtful and equivocal, if not mostly false and contradictory to former accounts; and observed, that in his manner of giving a detail of almost all distempers incident to the human body, in a progression from the head to the foot, without any distinguishing marks to know when they proceeded from the scurvy, and when from other causes, he **has acted much more irrationally than Eugalenus**; who, although he ascribes as many diseases to the scorbutic taint, yet gives the peculiar characteristics of pulse and urine proper almost to each; by which they may be known to proceed from that, and no other cause, which **Willis** no where does.

He indeed opens a little the mystery of his book towards the conclusion of it, in the relation of the case of a nobleman, which seems to have been as different from the scurvy as from the pox. "As this case, says he, cannot properly be referred to any other disease, it may justly be deemed scorbutic."

Dr. **Willis** is copied by most of the succeeding authors, especially by Charleton; by *Hoffman*, in the distribution of the symptoms; and by *Boerhaave*, in the grand distinction into a hot and cold scurvy, in the process of cure, as also in the medicines prescribed for it. But those already mentioned, having been deemed the standard and original writers on this subject, I shall not trouble the reader with any farther animadversions upon them or their followers. I am persuaded, that many other observations will naturally occur to those who peruse Part III. of this treatise with attention.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/14/mode/2up>

p.18-19

And as the shops abounded with antiscorbutic medicines of different and opposite virtues, taken from all parts of the animal, mineral, and vegetable kingdoms, it was proper to distinguish for what particular symptoms, diseases, or stages of the disease, each was peculiarly adapted.

But it may be asked, In what disease did such distinctions become so necessary? And it evidently appears, in that alone *which was first described by Eugalenus, and from him transcribed by Horstius and Sennertus; and has been described by Willis, and his copier Charleton*. But if the critical remarks that have been made upon these

original authors are admitted, the distinctions made here are founded in absurdity; and the former chapter is a sufficient confutation of them. These indeed, when first introduced by **Willis**, were not universally received. *Chameau*, with great strength of reason, confutes **Willis's** hypothesis; as many others have done.

But of multiplying divisions and classes of the scurvy there became no end. In which *Gideon Harvey*, physician to king *Charles II.* seems to have exceeded all others.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/18/mode/2up>

p.20-21

First, The galenical qualities of heat and cold, which **Willis** describes a *sulphureo-saline*, and a *salino sulphureous state of humours*; and which the more modern writers have distinguished by the appellation of *alcaline* and *acid scurvies*, were introduced; and the distinction continues to this day. By which they mean, that the scurvy occurs in different constitutions and habits of body, or at different times; proceeding from as opposite causes as can well be imagined; as from heat and cold, or the opposite qualities of an *acid* and *alcali*: and accordingly the different kinds of it require the most different methods of cure; what proves salutary in one species, being experienced hurtful, nay, poisonous in another. This was the consequence of *Eugalenus's* book, and other like writings.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/20/mode/2up>

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These authors, by confounding the two diseases, occasioned the utmost perplexity to succeeding writers on the subject. **Willis**, and all the followers of *Eugalenus*, maintain that the scurvy was nearly allied to the hypochondriac disease. But to set limits to both, and determine wherein they differed, puzzled authors not a little.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/22/mode/2up>

p.24-25

Boerhaave...

The whole indeed consists of scraps taken from different authors. He has picked the symptoms out of one book, *Sennertus's* collection, as he acquainted the pupils in his lectures; the cure out of another, viz. **Willis**. But it will appear to any person who peruses the authors from whom he

has borrowed the description of the symptoms, viz. *Echthius*, *Wierus*, &c. that they described a very different disease from what **Willis** did. Dr. **Willis's** method of cure may perhaps be rationally applied to the diseases he described; but is by no means adapted to the malady characterised by the first writers on the scurvy.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/24/mode/2up>

p.32-33

It is indeed a sufficient and just confutation of many writers on the scurvy, that they pretend to describe a malady to which seamen are peculiarly subject, and which they say proceeds from the diet used at sea, bad water, and sea-air. Yet their assertion, That the disease described by them (viz. *Eugalenus*, **Willis**, and their followers) is properly a marine disease, is refuted by the observation of all practitioners at sea. And the same may be said of the different species of scurvies alledged by *Boerhaave* to proceed from the causes above-mentioned.

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/32/mode/2up>

Lind 1757, 2nd ed: p.158-159

Some will perhaps say, that these fruits have been often used in the scurvy without success; as appears from the experience of physicians, who prescribe them every day in that disease at land. And here we may again observe the fatal consequence of confounding this malady with others. Legions of distempers (according to **Willis** and others) very different from the real and genuine scurvy, have been classed under its name: and because the most approved antiscorbutics fail to remove such diseases, hence we are told by authors, that it is the masterpiece of art to cure it. But this is contradicted by the daily experience of seamen, by the journals of our sea-hospitals, and by the yearly experience of our English East-India ships at St. Helena, and the Cape of Good Hope. So that nothing can be more absurd, than to object against the efficacy of these fruits in preventing and curing the real scurvy, because they do not cure very different diseases.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216015&seq=182>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=182>

https://archive.org/details/b30515622_0002/page/158/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/158/mode/2up>

The text below is from Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.364-370.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/364/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/364/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=388>

<https://hdl.handle.net/2027/ucm.5320216006>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=386>

Willis' text in Latin:

<https://archive.org/details/ned-kbn-all-00002727-001/page/n246/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b3034217x/page/226/mode/2up>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/zfhjwgem/items?canvas=251>

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He sets out with telling us, that a great variety of symptoms, and diseases of the most opposite kinds, are supposed to proceed from the scurvy; which, like a condemned and infamous name, has the scandal of most diseases charged to its account. How far he clears up this confusion, or has abridged the number, will appear by the following detail he gives of scorbutic symptoms. He observes, that no simple description or definition of this distemper can be given; and, consequently, that the best method of describing it, is according to the different parts affected of the body; in all which it produces manifold symptoms.

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He begins with the head: where the scurvy causes headaches, violent and habitual; and sometimes vague, or periodical; oftentimes sleepiness, and dulness of the spirits, at other times obstinate watchings; frequent giddiness, convulsions, palsies, salivations, ulcers of the gums, loose teeth, and fœtid breath.

The breast is affected with pains in different parts of its membranes, chiefly on the breast-bone, where they are very violent, acute, and darting; frequent asthma's; difficult and unequal respiration; straitness of the breast; violent cough; irregular pulse; palpitation of the heart; frequent faintings, and the continual dread of them.

In the *abdomen*, where this disease has its principal seat, it begets a multitude of evils, viz. *nausea*, vomiting, *cardialgia*, flatulencies, frequent colics, and most troublesome shifting pains; and almost constant purging, sometimes the dysentery, or *tenesmus*; the *atrophia*, and now and then the *ascites*. The urine is very often reddish and lixivial, having a cake suspended in it, or adhering to the sides of the glass: and sometimes, though seldom, a great quantity of pale watery urine is discharged.

In the limbs, or even over the whole body, there are wandering pains, often very acute, and becoming worse at night; a

lassitude; wasting of the flesh; pain of the back; a weakness of the other joints; spots of

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various colours on the skin; tumours, tubercles, and often malignant ulcers; a *stupor* or stinging pain about the muscles; a sense of cold as it were in the parts; contractions and *subsultus* of the tendons. Besides these, scorbutic people are subject to irregular effervescencies of the blood, irregular fevers, and profuse hæmorrhages. He concludes this long detail with observing, that these are the most common and usual symptoms of the scurvy, sometimes more, sometimes fewer, of this or that kind, afflicting the diseased: but besides what have been already mentioned, there occur in it more uncommon and extraordinary appearances.

The principal causes are, unwholesome air, and a vitiated texture of the blood by preceding sickness. In this distemper, either the blood, nervous juice, or both are affected. The fault of the blood is its being either *sulphureo-saline*, or *salino-sulphureous*. If the first be the case, and the sulphurs superabound, then repeated bleedings, a cooling regimen, and the most temperate remedies are proper; avoiding above all things the hot and acrid antiscorbutic medicines. But, on the contrary, where there is the *salino-sulphureous* state, and the salts of the blood are predominant, then the warmer medicines are proper, and such as are possessed of a volatile salt, together with steel

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and the like. The fault in the nervous juice is threefold. It is, 1st, Either too thin and poor; or, 2^{dly}, It has degenerated from its spirituous saline nature into a sharpness; or, 3^{dly}, It may abound with foreign and morbid particles. And according to these imagined faults in the blood and nervous juice, he makes a second distribution of the symptoms, and accounts for the whole number he enumerates in this disease, which he supposes to be hereditary and infectious.

The *indications* of cure are divided into three classes. 1. The preservative; under which he gives the process of cure, or

rather the method in general of removing the causes of the disease. 2. The curatory, or means of alleviating and relieving the most urgent symptoms. The 3d comprehends what he calls *the vital indications*, or the means of preserving and restoring the strength and health of the patient.

The cure is accomplished by purging, digestive and antiscorbutic medicines; with blood-letting occasionally repeated. If the stomach is much disordered, or oppressed with phlegm, he gives a vomit, weaker of stronger, according to the strength or habit of the patient. This in some he repeats every month, where it is indicated: otherwise he begins the cure with a purge, which he repeats occasionally, and of a different

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kind, suited to the warmer or colder constitution of the patient; or, to use his own terms, according as the *dyscrasy* of the blood is *sulphureo-saline*, or *nitro-sulphureous*. In both cases he furnishes us with variety of prescriptions; observing, that they should be repeated no oftener than at an interval of five or six days; as too violent and frequent purges serve only to weaken the tone of the *viscera*, and strength of the patient, without removing the disease. After once or twice purging, if a fulness of blood, and its viscidty, make it necessary, the patient is to be bled in the arm, or with leeches in the hæmorrhoidal veins; rather repeating the operation, than taking away too much at a time. Those evacuations being made according as they are severally indicated; provided no particular symptom be urgent, he proceeds to the general method of cure,

viz. removing the cause, and extirpating the disease. For these purposes, the digestive and specific antiscorbutic medicines (divided into two classes, *viz.* hot and cold) are to be given every day, unless when under the operation of a purge; to these, if needful, sweating medicines may be joined.²

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For the cold scurvy, he abounds with an ample variety of antiscorbutic compositions.³

In the hot scurvy, the more cooling and temperate antiscorbutics are necessary.⁴

2 He calls those *digestive medicines*, which assist or restore the functions of the stomach, and other chylopoietic *viscera*; and *antiscorbutics* or *specifics*, such as remove the scorbutic dyscrasy of the blood: both which are to be joined together, or at least given the same day. *Cremor, sal, or tinctura tartari, tartar. vitriol. chalybeat, el. propr.* &c. are proper digestives. They are to be administered in a small dose, evening and morning.

3 *Cochlearia, nasturtium aq. becabunga, cort. winteran. bacc. juniper. rad. raphani*, and other acrid aromatic herbs and roots, together with their conserves, the candied spices, *pulv. ari comp. steel, &c.* He has often successfully, prescribed the following remedy. *R. sum. genistæ manip. iii. minutim incis. Coquant. in cerevif. fort. lib. iii. ad medietatem.* Two or three ounces to be given twice a-day.

4 Of these he gives the same variety; making use, in most prescriptions, of the *testaceous* powders, the absorbents, *sal. absinth. &c.* He recommends wines made of goose berries, and other summer fruits, but especially cyder: observes *rad. lapathi acuti* to be among the best of our antiscorbutics. This infused in ale, with brook-lime, water-cresses, sliced oranges, citrons, pine-tops, &c. makes a noble remedy.

After having delivered the cure of the disease in general, he proceeds to the indications for removal of the most urgent symptoms.⁵

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He afterwards relates a symptom which he had observed three or four times, *viz.* a crackling of the bones upon moving the joints. Even upon turning in bed, by the rubbing of the bones of the back on each

other, a considerable noise was perceived, like to the rough handling of a skeleton; which he remarks is an almost incurable symptom.

Lastly, We have what he calls the *vital indications*. He here directs the use of cordials, restoratives, opiates, &c. together with a proper diet. He blames the immoderate use of sugar in the present age, for the frequency and violence of the scurvy; and concludes with some histories of cases.

5 For a difficulty of breathing, and asthmatic fits, he recommends cardiacs and antispasmodics, *viz. sp. corno cervi, tinct. castor. flor. benzoin. el. propr. &c.* given in any scorbutic liquor. If the *dyspnea* be entirely spasmodic, opiates afford the greatest relief: acrid glysters, sudorifics, and diuretics, are likewise serviceable. In scorbutic disorders of the stomach, vomits, purges of rhubarb, *el. propr. &c.* with fomentations to the part, are necessary: opiates sometimes give ease. In scorbutic colics, glysters are to be given; fomentations, liniments, and cataplasms, used externally; and opiates internally, especially when joined with purgatives: the *testaceous* powders are proper; likewise the use of some purging mineral water, as *Epsom*. An inveterate *diarrhea*, such as scorbutic persons are subject to, is not to be stopt by astringents: the mineral waters impregnated with steel and vitriol, are in this case the best medicines; and next to these, preparations of steel, especially its *crocus*. A *vertigo*, faintings, pally, and convulsions, require a mixture of cephalic and antiscorbutic remedies. The other symptoms are to be treated likewise with such medicines as are proper for the original diseases compounded with antiscorbutics.